

Spatio-Temporal Changes in Cropping Pattern in Satara District

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Abstract;

India is known as an agricultural country of villages. India's one third population directly and indirectly depends on agricultural sector and agriculture plays significant role in Indian economy. But present scenario shows that the Indian agricultural passing through difficult phase all over country. Due to the attitude of farmers is changed toward the high value crops. The cropping pattern means the proportion of area under different crops at the point of time.

The changes in cropping pattern reflected to change in land utilization under different crops at two different times. Due to the infrastructural development, technology, irrigation facilities, hybrid seeds, capital, transportation facilities, agro based industries, availability of marketing and diversification of agriculture changes occurred in cropping pattern. This study focused spatio temporal changes in cropping pattern in Satara district from 2001 to 2021.

The result is obtained from statistical and graphical analysis of the crop production in the study region. Besides these this study also found the area under food grain crops decreased and increased under cash crops like as Sugarcane. The Sugarcane cultivation record tremendous growths compare other crops.

Key Words: Spatio-temporal, Agriculture, Food grain, Cash crops.

Introduction:-

Today, Indian economy known as developing economy and more depend on the agricultural sector. Therefore, we usually say agriculture is back bone of Indian economy. India having second largest population in the world and majority of population lived in villages all over the country. Agriculture is prime sector to supply sufficient food and employment of Indian people. Agriculture sector supplied not only food for increasing population but also raw material for the agro based industries.

But the growths of industries are more than double than the agriculture sector. Today the agricultural sector provides 62 % direct and indirect employment and the 38 % by industrial sector. It is clearly shows that the rate of supply of employment by agriculture sector is more than double than the industrial sector.

But day by day the role of agriculture sector in national income marked decreasing trend, due to the agriculture achieved adequate water because of pressure from rapid growth of population, industrialization, urbanization and climate change. The gamble of monsoon, inadequate irrigation insufficient and ineffective implementation of government policies are marked about them. With

the increasing the small families the size of land holding decreases with more demand of agricultural production.

The choice of cropping pattern in a particular region is an outcome of i) the general condition of agriculture including types of soil, climate, water supply, water table. ii) The aim of agricultural production including size of land, scale of production, techniques of agriculture and changes in market price. The area having scarcity of rainfall having grater dependency on food grain like as Jawar, Bajara and etc. crops.

The area having assured rainfall and irrigation facilities are devoted to Sugarcane, Rice and Ginger crops. The black soil offers high production of Cotton and wheat crops, whereas laterite soil attracted plantation crops. Besides these rent of interest, wages and distance of market are the factors affecting on the cropping pattern.

2. Study Region:-

The study Satara district is one of the district of Maharashtra states. The agriculture is important activity in economic sector of Satara district. More than 70 % population depends on agriculture. The district has located in the Nira and Krishna basin.

Map of Study Region;

Fig No. 1

This district is located between 17° 5' to 18° 11' north latitudes, and 73° 33' to 74° 54' east longitudes and occupies an area of 1048489 sq.km. The study region has 2796906 populations. The study region lies in southern Maharashtra and administratively consists of 11 taluks which is Phaltan, Man, Khatav, Koregaon, Satara, Karad, Patan, Javali, Mahabaleshwar, Wai, and Khandala etc. In proposed study region the soil of farm is laterite patches in the west, to deep medium black alluvial of the river tracks and poor gray soil in the east part. The annual rainfall in the district varies from west to east. In the west Mahabaleshwar records highest amount of rainfall. It is 6000 mm. recorded, and it decreases in the east Man taluks, it is recorded 500 mm. The district having three seasons of rains which is June to September south-west monsoon, October to December having returning monsoon and March to May constitutes pre monsoon. The physical setting of district indicates contrast in temperature 11.7° C minimum and 37.5° C maximum. This has resulted variety of landscape, climate and agricultural activity. The

literacy rate is according to 2011 is 78.27 %, which is higher than state and nation too i. e. 77.27 % and 65.36 % respectively. The sex-ratio according to 2011 is 995, which is higher than state and nation too i. e. 992 and 933 per thousand male respectively. The western part of district is hilly region and eastern part is drought prone area. In the western part Mahabaleshwar, Wai, Patan, Javali, taluks having large forest area. In the study region Krishna and Koyana are main rivers and rivers basin has highly cultivable area in the district. In the eastern part including Man, Khatav, Phaltan, Khandala and some part of Koregaon, there is drought prone area and always shortage of drinking water.

Objective:-

The present study identifies to the valuable importance of cropping pattern and its spatio-temporal changes and check the important cash crops in Satara District.

Data Base and Methodology:-

The present study is based primary and secondary data. The primary data obtained from observation and field work method. The secondary

data obtained from district socio-economic review of Satara district. Thus, the data collected were processed and converted in percentage by statistical techniques. For result obtained the tabulated data shown by graphs.

Changes in Area under Major Crops in Satara District:-

The gross cropped area increased in the study period. The area under rice, Maize and wheat

crops increased with 35.5 to 50%. The share of Jawar and Bajara records decreasing trend. All the cash crops like Ginger and Sugarcane witnessed tremendous growth in net sown area as well as gross cropped area of the district. The table No. 1 shows area under the major crops and its changes in the district.

Table No. 1
Changes in Area Under Major Crops in Satara District

Crops	Area (Ha) '00'		Variation of Percentage
	2010-11	2019-20	
Jawar	735.82	380.29	- 49.30
Bajara	981.09	643.89	- 35.41
Wheat	652.39	1045.17	34.12
Rice	536.34	826.06	32.13
Maize	453.53	1035.94	122.24
Ginger	608.48	1328.92	135.21
Sugarcane	649.25	1957.71	311.32
Others	1656.07	1176.97	- 34.52
Total	6273	8395	

Source: Compiled form by author (Socio-economic Review of Satara district)

Changes in Area under Major Crops in Satara District

Fig No. 3

Percentage Distribution of Major Crops in Satara district:-

The table No 1 shows land use pattern of Satara district. The Table No. 1 and fig. No. 2

clearly shows that in the year 2000-01 to 2020-21, percentage of food grain crops has been decreasing trend, whereas cash crops recorded increasing trend. The total cropped area in the

Table No. 2
Percentage Distribution of Major Crops in Satara district

Year	Total Cropped Area (Ha)	Jawar	Bajara	Wheat	Rice	Maize	Ginger	Sugarcane	Others
2010-11	6273	11.73	15.64	10.40	8.55	7.23	9.70	10.35	26.40
2019-20	8395	4.53	7.67	12.45	9.84	12.34	15.83	23.32	14.02
Variation	2122	-7.2	-7.97	2.05	1.29	5.11	6.13	12.97	7.38

Source: Compiled form by author (Socio-economic Review of Satara district)

Percentage Distribution of Major Crops in Satara district

Fig No. 2

District recorded more than double area under Ginger and Sugarcane cultivation. Within study periods the land utilization of food grain crops like Jawar and Bajara turned into the cash crops like as Ginger and Sugarcane. The area under wheat, rice and maize also marked increasing trend but cash crops like Ginger and Sugarcane shows tremendous growth in gross cropped area.

Perspective Changes in Cropping Pattern:-

The country India having sugarcane cultivation great history and India is second largest country in the world in sugarcane production. The sugarcane cultivation acquire more than 7 % share in Indian economy. Besides these this crop supply raw material to the other industries. The Maharashtra is 2nd position in sugarcane cultivation, and the Uttar Pradesh having 1st position. The western Maharashtra including Satara, Sangali, Pune, Solapur, Kolhapur and Ahmadnagar districts leads to sugar industries by co-operative as well as private sector. In the district Satara having 11 co-operative 7 private sugar industries. The crop sugarcane having more than 23 % area in the district. The basin of Krishna, Koyana and Nira having highly cultivable soil, irrigation facilities and installation of the sugar industries in this area.

Conclusion:-

In the study region Satara district the attitude of the farmers changed towards cash crops in the study period. The cash crops sugarcane cultivation marked increasing trend with more than double. This crop using 50 % of the water by irrigation facilities. Besides these cultivation of Ginger and Maize records increasing trend. The trend of food grain crops like as Jawar and Bajara marked decreasing trend which are create insecurity for food in future of the district. The responsible authority required steps to divert the attention of farmers towards fruit farming in all over the study region.

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